

ECO STP 2023

6th IWA International Conference
on **eco-Technologies for
Wastewater Treatment**

GIRONA- SPAIN
26th-29th June

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

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Following the previous successful IWA ecoSTP conferences (Spain 2012, Italy 2014, UK 2016, Canada 2018, Italy 2021), it is our great pleasure to welcome you to the 6th IWA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment to be held from June 26th to 29th, 2023 in Girona.

ecoSTP-23 aims to discuss the latest cutting-edge eco-technologies for a sustainable transition in wastewater treatment, reuse, and resource recovery, at urban and industrial scale, giving special attention to the efficient transfer of knowledge into practice. Building a more resilient future for water management needs a transdisciplinary and multi-domain examination, including socio-economic and governance aspects. ecoSTP23 will include hydro-social aspects and the multiple factors that currently frame water management.

Maite Pijuan and Ignasi Rodriguez-Roda

Co-chairs of ecoSTP23

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Navigating towards an innovative and
sustainable water industry

Gustaf Olsson
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Water - key indicator of global
warming and basis for energy and
food production

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PROGRAM

Fe- and Zn-biochar mediated carbamazepine removal via heterogeneous Fenton process

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Abstract

In this work, the removal of carbamazepine in an aqueous solution was performed using the Fenton process catalyzed with Fe-BC and Zn-BC. The research included synthesis of catalysts and optimization of pharmaceutical removal conditions using the *Definitive screening design* statistical method in order to achieve the maximum efficiency of the mentioned treatment. Both materials showed good catalytic performance in the applied treatment (~98%). Obtained effluents showed high toxicity inhibition percent (~80%), as well as mineralization measured as TOC~80%. The further step is characterization of effluents using ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC)-high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) method.

Keywords

biochar-based catalyst; degradation; Fenton; carbamazepine;

INTRODUCTION

Carbamazepine (CBZ) is classified as a persistent organic pollutant, because its removal efficiency in water treatment plants is about 10%. It is toxic even at concentrations below 100 mg/l. Therefore, there is a need to find an efficient technology for its removal from the aquatic environment.

The Fenton process is one of the most effective advanced oxidation processes and is used to treat water with a high content of complex organic matter, as well as other non-biodegradable compounds. The use of Fenton's reagent increases the degradability of complex organic compounds in wastewater, which results in their conversion into organic compounds of low molecular weight, or complete mineralization, until the formation of carbon dioxide and water. Increasing attention is focused on the use of biochar as a catalyst in order to use sewage sludge as a resource, not the waste. Due to its low cost, large specific surface area and good stability, biochar is a promising material that can be compared with other carbon materials. It has been often applied as carrier to improve the performance of iron and other ions impregnated in the carbon matrix. In this work, the removal of carbamazepine was performed using the Fenton process catalyzed by modified biochars, Fe-BC and Zn-BC. The test included the synthesis of biochar and the optimization of the conditions for the degradation of CBZ, using the Fenton process, with varying doses of hydrogen peroxide, CBZ and prepared catalysts, as well as pH and reaction time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the synthesis of biochar, the final sludge from the wastewater treatment plant in the settlement of Kovilj (near Novi Sad), Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia was used. The biochar preparation procedure was performed according to Chen et al. (2020). Impregnation with iron and Zn onto biochar was performed according to the conventional method (Iurascu et al., 2009; Azmi et al., 2014). A BET analyzer (AutoSorb iQ2) was used to characterize the synthesized materials in order to test the specific surface area. To optimize the process conditions, the statistical method of *Definitive screening design (DSD)*, was assessed in order to achieve the maximum efficiency of the applied treatment and the degradation of the selected pollutant. The tests were carried out by a series of experiments on JAR test apparatus (FC6S Velp scientific, Italy). The

absorbance (A) was measured at a wavelength of CBZ $\lambda_{max} = 285$ nm. Determining the absorption maxima (λ_{max}) by recording the spectrum of the CBZ solution, as well as monitoring the change in absorbance during the experiments, was performed using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Toxicity of samples was tested with the *Aliivibrio fischeri* bacteria bioluminescence test according to protocol ISO 11348-3 (2007). The principal of the test is to measure the bioluminescence of the bacteria before and after the addition of test samples, compared to control, at different time rates, 5, 15 or 30 minutes. The mineralization of effluents was determined using TOC analyzer (liquiTOC II, Elementar, Germany) (SRPS ISO 8245:2007).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impregnation of the pristine biochar with Fe (III) (BET= 3.807 m²/g) and precipitation with Zn (II) ions (BET= 104.7 m²/g) influenced the increase of the specific surface areas of the pristine material (BET= 57.83 m²/g). The basic scheme of the experiment, obtained by applying the DSD model with 5 numerical factors, consists of 12 experiments and 2 central points (Table 1).

Table 1. Matrix of experiment with achieved CBZ removal efficiencies

Sample	Removal efficiency (%)	
	Fe-BC	Zn-BC
1	78	79
2	87	85
3	88	58
4	84	79
5	1	81
6	88	85
7	83	87
8	7	90
9	0.2	95
10	79	85
11	79	88
12	88	93
13	96	96
14	96	98

The results of testing the efficiency of the Fenton process in the removal of carbamazepine are shown in Table 4, where the range of removal efficiency was established from 0.2% to 96% for Fe-BC, from 58% to 98% for the Zn-BC catalyst. The achievement of maximum and minimum removal efficiency in the Fenton process at different set of process conditions is observed, thus confirming the assumption that the drug removal process itself largely depends on the applied experimental conditions, as well as on the applied materials. During the experiment, very significant removal efficiency was observed in the Fenton process at a different set of process conditions, which established that the removal process itself depends on the applied experimental conditions and used catalysts. An exception exists in 3 experiments in the case of Fe-BC, when the efficiency was low (up to 7%).

Optimization diagrams of the Fenton process are shown in Figures 1 and 2. They give a clear insight into how the selected process parameters affect the dependent variable, i.e. drug removal efficiency. The statistical model within the Fenton process for Fe-BC suggests a high

carbamazepine removal efficiency of 95.885% under the following optimal conditions: pH=5.5, drug concentration of 5.5 mg/l, catalyst concentration of 60 mg/l, hydrogen concentration -peroxide of 10.5 mM and a reaction time of 105 min.

Figure 1. Optimization diagram of the Fenton process catalyzed by Fe-BC

Additionally, the statistical model within the Fenton process for Zn-BC suggests a high carbamazepine removal efficiency of 97.09% under the following optimal conditions: pH=5.5, drug concentration of 5.5 mg/l, catalyst concentration of 60 mg/l, concentration of hydrogen peroxide of 10.5 mM, while the reaction time is not proposed by the model, assuming that it does not have a large effect on the efficiency of the removal of the selected drug, under the investigated conditions (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Optimization diagram of the Fenton process catalyzed by Zn-BC

It can be concluded that both biochars showed good catalytic performance under the applied conditions of the Fenton process. Toxicity measurements showed high inhibition percent (~85%) in both cases, pointing out on formation of toxic intermediates after Fenton reaction of 105 minutes. Further investigation will be conducted for longer reaction time, aiming on decreasing the effluent toxicity. Also, significant mineralization, measured as TOC, was achieved (~80%). The next step that will be implemented is the characterization of the obtained effluents after the optimal conditions using ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC)-high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) method.

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